

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

INFLUENCES OF PROJECTILE MATERIALS ON IMPACT RESISTANCE OF 2D TRIAXIAL BRAIDED COMPOSITES

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Introduction

- Two-dimensional (2D) **triaxial braided composite** materials have been used in the **fan blade and casing** of commercial aero-engines, such as GEnx engine.
- **Ballistic impact tests** on subscale and full-scale component enable designers to optimize the design of the composite structures in terms of weight saving.
- The **titanium alloy projectile**, especially in the **blade-like shape** is commonly used in the research of casing containment.
- Cylinder **gelatin projectile** has been extensively accepted that it could be employed to replace the real bird with the similar mass, density and compressibility during the impact tests, and describe the fluid behavior of bird under high velocity impact.
- Considering that the carbon fiber reinforced fan casing always accompanied by the composite fan blade, the dynamic response of triaxial braided composites impacted by **CFRP projectile** and its differences with metal and gelatin projectile is of great interest.
- In the current paper, **three types of projectile, including cylinder gelatin projectile, CFRP blade-like projectile and titanium alloy projectile**, were employed to conduct ballistic impact tests to identify the damage pattern and failure modes of the 2D triaxial braided composites. **The influences of projectile materials** on the damage pattern and energy absorption behavior are investigated

Ballistic impact test

□ The preparation of the composite target

- The composite target was braided with 12k T700 carbon fiber in the form angle of $[\pm 60^\circ/0^\circ]$.
- **Manufacture of perform:** a triaxial braider, mounted with the axis horizontal, creates a braid tube using 12k flat tow fibers both in the $\pm 60^\circ$ (bias) and 0° (axial) directions (a), then it was flattened into a double-walled tape (b). The 3 layers of flatten tapes were piled up with the 0° fibers aligned.
- **Curing process:** Triaxial braided composite panel was fabricated with RTM technique, in which epoxy resin was infused into triaxial braided preform. The fiber volume in each direction was equal, so that both the individual plies and the entire lay-up were quasi-isotropic.
- The composite target was cut out in **size of 250 mm x 250 mm**, with a **thickness of 4.3 mm**.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Ballistic impact test

□ Material and size of the projectiles

- Three types of projectile with the **same 25 g mass** were used in impact tests.
- The CFRP and titanium alloy projectiles are in the shape of **rectangular**, both with **the length of 70 mm and the width of 40 mm**.
- Considering the differences of density, **the CFRP projectile have thickness of 6 mm** while the **titanium alloy projectile have thickness of 2 mm**.
- The gelatin projectiles are in the shape of flat-ended cylinder, with diameter of 30 mm and height of 52 mm. The **equivalent diameter** of the gelatin cylinder is same as that of rectangular projectiles.

(a) CFRP projectile

(b) gelatin projectile

(c) titanium alloy projectile

Ballistic impact test

□ Testing device

- The **gas gun with 65 mm caliber** used in ballistic tests is able to accelerate the projectile to the **maximum velocity of 200m/s**.
- The projectile is supported by foam in an **aluminium sabot**. The sabot and projectile is pushed and accelerated by **compressive air** in the gun barrel. The projectile launch velocity varies by changing the air pressure.
- The sabot is captured at the exit of gun barrel by a **sabot separator** while the projectile moves forward and impacts the target directly.
- The spallation fragments from the target, projectile with residual velocity and fragment of foam are arrested by the fragment collector mounted on the back of target.

Ballistic impact test

□ The mounting of projectile and composite plate

- The projectile is supported by foam in an aluminium sabot.
- The triaxial braided composite plate is fixed in both short edges through 4 screw bolts, leaving the upper and down edges free.

(a) projectile in the sabot

(b) the clamping of triaxial braided composite plates

Results and discussions

□ Results with CFRP projectile

- A total of six effective tests were carried out using the CFRP projectiles.
- The triaxial experiment target is perforated by the CFRP projectile at 157 m/s, and not perforated at 131 m/s, so the ballistic limit speed is between these two speeds.

Table 1 : High speed impact test results with CFRP projectiles

Testing number	Projectile mass /g	Launch pressure /Mpa	Impact velocity / (m/s)	Residual velocity / (m/s)	Test results	Energy absorption (J)
CFRP1	27.8	0.3	118	0	Rebound	193.54
CFRP2	26.7	0.66	168	123	Perforation	174.82
CFRP3	27.3	0.37	131	0	Rebound	234.25
CFRP4	28.2	0.55	172	108	Perforation	252.67
CFRP5	27.1	0.54	170	101	Perforation	253.37
CFRP6	26.1	0.45	157	45	Perforation	295.24

Results and discussions

□ Results with CFRP projectile

Typical damage in rebound case:

- After the impact of the projectile, a **rectangular sunken area** with the size of the cross section of the projectile is formed. The depth of the **sunken area** is shallow, without visible cracking or damage.
- On the exit surface of the triaxial braided target, there are also no visible matrix cracking, bending deformation or serious delamination.
- The target plate remained basically intact with **no visible damage**.

incident surface

exit surface

CFRP-3 test, Rebound, impact velocity of 131m/s

Results and discussions

□ Results with CFRP projectile

Typical damage in perforation case:

- The area of the **perforative opening** is slightly larger than the cross section of the CFRP projectile.
- The damage area on the impact surface is about 15~18 cm² surrounding the opening with slight damage and a certain degree of **cracking and delamination**.
- The damage on the **exit surface** of the projectile is much more serious, and the damage area is above 30 cm², which is about **twice the damage area on the impact surface**.

incident surface

exit surface

CFRP-6 test, Perforation, impact velocity of 157m/s

Results and discussions

□ Results with CFRP projectile

Impact process during perforation cases:

- at 1.65 ms, the CFRP projectile begins to contact the target plate, and almost pass through the target plate at 3.3 ms.
- The target plate **did not show obvious bending deformation** during the whole impact process, and the back of the target plate showed obvious smoke caused by **matrix fragmentation**.

(a)0.33ms

(b)1.65ms

(c)3.3ms

(d)5.28ms

The perforation process of CFRP projectile recorded by high speed camera

Results and discussions

□ Results with gelatin projectile

- Two sets of impact tests were performed using a cylindrical gelatin projectile. The impact velocity of the two tests were 169 m/s and 213 m/s respectively.
- However, even with impact velocity as high as 213 m/s, the 2D triaxial braided composites **were not perforated** by the gelatin projectile. **The gelatin projectile flow and fragment** during the impact on the contrary.

Table 2: High-speed impact test data of gelatin projectile

Testing number	Projectile mass /g	Launch pressure/ Mpa	Impact velocity / (m/s)	Residual velocity / (m/s)	Testing results	Energy absorption (J)
Gelatin-1	25.6	0.55	169	---	Projectile fragmentation	365.58
Gelatin-2	27	1	213	---	Projectile fragmentation	612.48

Results and discussions

□ Results with Gelatin projectile

Typical damage:

- At impact speed of 169m/s of gelatin projectile, the target plate has **no visible damage** on the impact surface, with hardly any dents, fiber breaks or delamination damage.
- At velocity of 213m/s, there are no obvious deformation or fiber breakage on the impact surface. However delamination, matrix cracking and **a small amount of fiber breakage** were observed on the **through-thickness direction** of the target. The damage on the exit surface of the target plate shows that there are **matrix cracking** at a distance from the impact point.

(a) Gelatin-1 test, impact velocity of 169 m/s

(b) Gelatin-2 test, impact velocity of 213 m/s

Results and discussions

□ Results with Gelatin projectile

Impact process with velocity of 213 m/s:

- The triaxial braided composite target undergoes **a large bending deformation** under the impact of the gelatin projectile, which **absorbs the energy** of the impact to a large extent.
- At the end of impact, the composite target plate was not perforated by the gelatin projectile, and the **bending deformation of the target plate was recovered** completely.
- The large bending deformation of the target during the impact result in **the delamination and matrix cracking of the target**.
- Since the **hardness of the gelatin projectile is lower** than that of the carbon fiber composite, there is no significant fiber breakage damage.

(a) 1.32ms

(b) 2.64ms

(c) 3.63ms

(d) 5.94ms

(f) 12.54ms

Results and discussions

□ Discussion

- The 2D triaxial braided composite target impacted with **the gelatin projectile** could **absorb much more energy than the CFRP projectile**.
- The main reason is that due to **the fluidity of the gelatin projectile** itself, **the contact area** with the target plate during impact **is much larger** than the impact area of the CFRP projectile impact.
- Consequently, **the impact energy could be more evenly transmitted to the entire target plate**. The **overall large bending deformation** of the target plate is generated, **dissipating more impact energy**.

Results and discussions

□ Results with titanium alloy projectile

- Three sets of impact tests were carried out using titanium alloy blade projectile.
- In the three sets of tests with impact velocity ranging at 105~160 m/s, the titanium alloy projectile perforated the target plate. The target has a **ballistic limit speed below 105 m/s**.

Table 3 : High-speed impact of titanium alloy projectile

Testing number	Projectile material	Projectile mass /g	Launch pressure/ Mpa	Impact velocity / (m/s)	Residual velocity/ (m/s)	Test results	Energy absorption (J)
Ti-1	Titanim alloy	24.8	0.5	160	118	Perforation	144.78
Ti-2	Titanim alloy	24.3	0.37	146	83	Perforation	175.29
Ti-3	Titanim alloy	25	0.2	105	23	Perforation	131.2

Results and discussions

□ Results with titanium alloy projectile

Typical damage at velocity of 105 m/s:

- there is a significant **shear fractured rectangular opening** on the incident surface, and the area and shape are substantially the same as the cross-sectional area of the titanium alloy projectile, which is quite small and thin.
- On the exit surface of the target, there is **an elliptical bulged damage area**. The damage area shows obvious damage modes such **as fiber breakage, matrix cracking and delamination**.
- Compared with the CFRP projectile, the damage area is more **concentrated** and the area of the **damage zone is smaller** (about 15cm²).

(a) Incident surface

(b) Exit surface

Results and discussions

□ Results with titanium alloy projectile

Impact process with velocity of 105 m/s:

- The projectile is in a **ideal posture** before hitting the target plate.
- The contact with the target plate **begins at 5.28 ms**.
- At 12.21 ms, about 2/5 of the blade projectile in the length passed through the target
- at 21.12 ms, the titanium alloy projectile **completely passed through** the target.
- During the entire impact process of the titanium alloy blade projectile, **the bending deformation** of the target plate **is limited**, which is quite different with that in cases impact with gelatin projectile. This also explains **that the damage of the target plate is concentrated and the energy absorption is low.**

(a) 0.33 ms

(b) 5.28 ms

(c) 12.21 ms

(d) 21.12 ms

Results and discussions

□ Results with titanium alloy projectile

Typical damage at velocity of 160 m/s:

- Due to the fact that the blade projectile has a **certain yaw angle** when it exits, an open-type tear occurs on the incident surface of the projectile.
- The **damage on the back side** of the target plate is more serious, the damage area is about twice that of the incident surface, and there **is obvious fiber breakage and delamination**.

(a) Incident surface

(b) Exit surface

Results and discussions

□ Comparison of different projectile materials

- The ballistic limit velocity of CFRP projectile is between 131 m/s~157 m/s, the ballistic limit velocity of gelatin projectile is above 213 m/s, while the ballistic limit velocity of titanium alloy projectile is below 105 m/s.
- The variation of energy absorption of 2D triaxial braided composites with the impact velocity is plotted.
- The target could **absorb much more energy when impacted with soft gelatin projectiles**, while it **absorbs the least energy when impacted with titanium projectiles**. The CFRP projectile lead to moderate energy absorption.

Energy absorption of triaxial braided composites impacted with incident velocity

Results and discussions

□ Comparison of different projectile materials

- The composite target has **the highest energy absorption (above 612 J)** when impacted with gelatin projectile. Since the composite target was not perforated at this speed, the energy absorption **has not reached its critical value**.
- When the composite target was impacted with CFRP and titanium alloy blade-like projectile, the energy absorption of the composite target **increases firstly and then decreases** with the increase of the **impact velocity**.
- When the triaxial braided composite was impacted with CFRP projectile, the maximum energy absorption is 295 J, **lifted for 68%** compared with the value impacted with titanium alloy projectile (maximum value of 175 J).

Energy absorption of triaxial braided composites impacted with different projectile

Conclusions

In this paper, the ballistic impact test of 2D triaxial braided composite target plate was carried out using three types of projectile of generally same mass. The effects of projectile material on the impact resistance of the target were investigated, and the main conclusions were drawn:

- ❑ When impacted with **the CFRP blade-like projectile**, the damage of tri-axial braided composites on the impact surface is **rectangular opening** with the shape and size same as the projectile head. The **bulged damage area on the exit surface** is larger and more severe with massive fiber breakages, fiber pull-out, severe matrix cracking and delamination.
- ❑ **The gelatin projectile** exhibits **fluid behavior** after impact, and the response of the target plate is dominated by the **overall deformation**. The composite target were not damaged at the impact and exit surface, but **delamination failure** occurred. The energy absorption of 2D triaxial braided target is up to 612J when impacted with the gelatin projectile.
- ❑ Under the impact of the CFRP projectile, the energy absorption (up to 295 J) of the 2D triaxial braided target plate is 68% higher than that of the titanium alloy projectile (up to 175 J). Therefore, it can be seen that **the combination use of the composite fan blade and casing could achieve a better weight reduction effect.**

Thanks for your attention!

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